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Navigating the Ethical Issues with Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Evangelism in the 21st Century Church

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Abstract

This research, navigating the ethical issues with Artificial Intelligence (AI) and evangelism in the 21st century Church, underscored the moral considerations in relation to evangelism and the emerging technological advancements like AI today. The work focused on providing the Church with much-needed technological tools and ethical guidelines for engaging Artificial Intelligence (AI) in the 21st century evangelism. The relevance of Christian Churches and the mode of operation in the twenty-first century is much more different from what it used to be in the previous centuries. Technological advancement affects our lives and forces a shift to a more progressive era. These shifts will happen increasingly faster as development and technological breakthroughs increase; and at the same time come with lots of ethical and theological issues that challenge the status quo. This crisis, occasioned by the emergence of these new technologies has much to do with changing contexts of the existing praxis of the Church. Using descriptive phenomenology and secondary sources of data collection and analysis, this paper, uncovered that, while AI and other technological givens are relevant to evangelism in the 21st century, its ethical implications should be taken into consideration at every point in time. The work advised the Church to leverage Artificial Intelligence (AI) in the advancement of the gospel truth, to avoid being left behind or remaining in the old tradition. It noted however that, the fast-changing technological landscape will require shifts from the Christian community in all aspects and the Church must take advantage of this to advance its evangelical actions bearing in mind the ethical and theological implications involved.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence (AI), Ethics, Evangelism, 21st Century, Church Praxis, Techno-hermeneutics

Introduction

The experience of COVID-19, redefined the perspectives, practice and relevance of Church of the 21st century in all facets, especially, in the use of technology to advancing her mission. The Church realized more clearly that her mission was not just restricted within the walls but far beyond that; and to reach out to the wider audience, the essence of engaging technology, became very imperative. The lessons learnt within the period and after, have fostered massive deployment of various new technologies including AI, in the advancement of the frontiers of the Kingdom of God. Today many Christian denominations, including those in the rural communities have employed relevant technologies in their evangelical activities.

Using technological developments like Artificial Intelligence (AI) in evangelism does not come without challenges. Watkins (2001), noted that, "the Church has always been cautious of emerging technologies, for example, the barcode, credit cards and microchips, labelling them in conspiracy terms as part of a satanic plan to connect Christians to the beast of Revelation 13. During the COVID-19 pandemic, nanobots, nanotechnology, radio frequency identification (RFID) chips and other digital tracking devices were said to be hidden in the COVID-19 vaccine. This supported the conspiracy theory of the time and the vaccine became the new suspect (Thomas & Zhang, 2020). This implied a flawed understanding of technology and has created a possible misgiving between the Church and the advancement of technology. Citing Barrat (2013), Etienne (2024) noted that, "there is a mismatch between AI development and the Church. Although many

people warn about the associated risks of exponential AI development, the Church is still not properly positioned to understand and respond with ethical guidance and direction.”

Radner (2020) stated that, “although intelligent technologies like AI can solve complex ethical issues like more accurate health diagnostics and greener development, the fundamental criteria in considering the use of AI as Christians has to be the law of God according to the Scriptures, and God’s self-revelation in the incarnate Christ.” The advancement of AI technology will come with it, the moral and ethical temptations like the worshipping of machines and sex robots that have never existed in the history of humanity (Cox-George & Bewley, 2018).

The major objective of this research, is to examine the importance of engaging Artificial Intelligence (AI) in evangelism by the Church, with a view to underscoring the ethical issues arising from such engagement. In that regard, there is need for the Church to develop a techno-hermeneutics or ethical guidelines to comprehend and explain the ethical issues associated with Artificial Intelligence (AI). Else, the 21st century Church does not stand a better chance in playing a defining role in the unfolding technological future. It is therefore imperative for the Church not to keep postponing its responsibility to develop a techno-hermeneutics and ethics guidelines to assist Christians through the century under review and beyond. This will go a long way in assisting the Church in spreading the Gospel truth everywhere. The 21st century Church, stands a better chance in using AI in all aspects of mission; but must be willing to understand and navigate through the ethical challenges that may arise as a result. In the next sub-heading, the researcher explains briefly the key concepts.

Explicating the Concepts of Artificial Intelligence (AI), Ethics and Evangelism

AI refers to machines that imitate human intelligence. It is featured with programmed algorithms, to enable the machines think and behave like humans. The term may also be applied to any machine that exhibits traits associated with the human brain, such as learning and problem solving (Proqis, 2021). There are two forms of AI. Strong AI and weak AI. Strong AI refers to machines that can think like humans, whereas weak AI refers to machines that act as if they are intelligent (Kumar & Thakur, 2012). AI simulates human intelligence by programming machines to think and act like humans. The term can also refer to machines that display human-like qualities such as learning and problem solving (Proqis, 2021).

Ethics, simply means, the science of morality. It is a systematic theory of the nature of the moral life of man; that is to say, the norms of right and wrong by which man’s conduct may be guided (Nwankwo, 2024). It has to do with the reflected doings and morality of the human person. Thus, it is the scientific study of the behavioural patterns of the human person with special reference to his or her nature as rational being. It seeks to device reasons for approving or condemning human acts as right or wrong, good or bad, and as worthy or unworthy of a rational being (Echekwube, 2005).

Nwankwo and Emeahara (2024), citing Green (1992), affirmed that, “the term evangelism comes from the phrase ‘preaching the Gospel.’” The single word evangelism is used rather than the phrase “Preaching the Gospel.” But both have the same meaning. Evangelism is based on the gospel of Jesus Christ. The term is deeply related to Jesus Christ and it means nothing without Him. Therefore, the meaning of the term should be sought in the New Testament, beginning with the coming of Jesus Christ. Evangelism may involve preaching, or Bible distribution, tracts, spiritual newspaper, and or magazines, by the media or other means. Engaging AI in evangelism by the 21st century considers the gains of using advanced technology in propagating the Gospel of the Kingdom and covering wider grounds. This involvement of AI does not come without ethical implications and challenges, which must be taken into consideration. As artificial intelligence (AI) develops into more sophisticated technologies, the voices warning against its possible risks grow louder. The Church’s role to bring hope, to establish emotional and spiritual stability, and to equip and guide, will become vital in the 21st century (Barrat, 2013).

Artificial Intelligence (AI) Technology and the 21st Century Church

The Church and her message in history, has been subjected to scorn, disbelief and persecution, yet its good news, thriving under God's Spirit, has endured (Guzman, 2023). This has been the case even in the 21st century with the disruptive incursion of advanced technology pervading all strata of human existence.

The swift expansion and sway of artificial intelligence has started to make waves beyond the marketplace and into places of worship, specifically the Church. The application of such advanced technology in a traditionally human-led sphere raises profound questions about the combination of tradition and modernity, faith and science. It forces man to confront the boundaries of AI's role and potential implications it has on faith-based practices and rituals, like evangelism. Schrock (2023), noted that, "The Church tends to lag about 10 years behind the secular world when it comes to technology adoption."

AI, when viewed solely as a tool, can be seen as a gift from God to help Church leader in many practical and time-saving ways in the 21st century. This can be seen in areas like: sermon research, chatbots on websites, social media content creation, among others. However, some Christians view the development of AI as an attempt by the creation to become the Creator. Thus, Pope Francis warned: "the urgent need to educate people on the concept and use of artificial intelligence in a responsible way, so that it may be at the service of humanity and the protection of man's common home, requires that ethical reflection be extended to the sphere of education and law." (Schrock, 2023).

In that regard, the 21st century Church should engage AI as loyal servant and as a tool that has the potential to significantly aid the Christian Church in accomplishing its mission in various areas such as: Analysing and understanding scriptures, digital pastoral care and humanitarian support, streamlining administrative tasks, enhancing outreach and evangelism, creating sermons, predictive analytics for Church growth, prayer request management, language translation in a virtual Church (Etienne, 2024).

Leveraging Artificial Intelligence (AI) for Effective Evangelism in the 21st Century

Afolaranmi (2019) said that, "the world we live in today has metamorphosed from an analog world to a digital one where technological tools are taking significant roles. More people (even the so-called illiterate) are now using technological tools in their day-to-day activities." Where people live does not matter anymore. Whether they are in the farthest villages among old people or in the urban setting among the young generation; to expand the gospel message, all hand must be on deck in the area of embracing technology to achieve this.

Gunter (1991), said that, "if one takes mission and evangelism out of the Bible, the Bible will simply be left with only its covers." This signifies that mission and evangelism are paramount and of great importance in the Bible. Mission is the heart-beat of God. The Church of the 21st century should employ all within her capacity, including Artificial Intelligence, in core missionary enterprise to extending the gospel truth to all nooks and crannies of the society (Afanugo and Molokwu, 2024).

It is quite obvious that many people today are embracing technology in different dimensions to achieve their ends, the Church is not entirely left out. Fagunwa (2015) observed that Christians nowadays read online spiritual books frequently. This goes to affirm the fact that technology in itself is neutral and should be involved at every stage of Church activities for the growth of the Church. Leveraging Artificial Intelligence by the Church in the 21st century will enhance the massive production of online easy to read Christian spiritual and devotional books that can reach a wider audience within the society's local communities. However, various factors have been adduced to work against a better and wider use of AI by the Church missions. This include but not limited to: poor infrastructure, lack of information and communication technology, computer literacy, lack of trained human resources, the high cost of AI facilities and the illiteracy level of most Church members (Afanugo and Molokwu, 2024).

In the light of underscoring the importance of AI in evangelism, George (2023), noted that, “Artificial Intelligence and social media have disrupted the mode of evangelism by the Church; hence the Church ought to align with the new order, ensuring the love of Jesus Christ is preached to the world through the new media.” Studies show that many local communities in Nigeria and other African nations have adopted respectively the “vicilook technology,” that provides the public with digital information and access of only verified Church priests and Church branches around the globe. This is commendable as the ‘vicilook Qr codes’ (an application that helps anyone find, connect and verify within the environment) connects one to all the Church branches, Church missionary institutions and ventures of a peculiar locality (Afanugo and Molokwu, 2024). This tech substitutes the popular Church directory and lectionary booklet and also gives anyone around the globe online open access to any verified missionary activity carried out by the Church across the globe.

It is important to note also that, a well programmed AI in Church missionary enterprise can easily prepare sermons of any length both audio and written. AI can easily detect potential threats at mission target locations. AI can also easily detect and ascertain within the mission focus zone, areas with people that are susceptible to the gospel message in order to first prioritize evangelization therein. This will afford missionaries, evangelist and Church planters, the opportunity of training leaders that will help them in evangelization to other areas within the zone. AI can equally be programmed to easily detect aspects of a given mission target area, like culture, that can serve as a window to communicate the gospel messages across the globe (Afanugo and Molokwu, 2024).

Andre (2024), accentuated ways through which AI could be used to further evangelism and mission by the 21st century Church. These include: connecting with people in their language, creating a personalized content and, enhancing and expanding the existing staff or manpower.

One of the most helpful uses of AI for ministry is in the area of language translation. With AI in space, missionaries do not need to spend time and resources on manual translations, rather, they focus on other aspects of sharing resources like delivery and impact, while relying on AI to do the bulk of translation work. AI can help translate messages as fast as possible. This will go a long way in assisting missionaries in intercultural environment with ease of evangelism and reaching the people.

AI can help streamline the creation of videos, emails or event flyers quickly, creatively and effectively. Leveraging AI can assist to personalize touch points with many people and enhancing daily outreach efforts. Finally, AI tools can help a single person expand their capacity. By integrating AI into the workflow, the Church can extend her reach and amplify her efforts, effectively turning a limited team into a more efficient and productive force (Andre, 2024).

GodKulture Team (2023), posed a question, “is AI the next evangelism frontier for the Church?” He went on to assert that, “if properly used, artificial intelligence can be a formidable ally to help the Church reach wider audiences across the globe.” Involving AI in evangelism is a great idea, however, the 21st century Church must be cautious in the matters regarding to ethics and morality, while considering AI. This concern, shall dominate the discussion in the next sub-heading.

Ethical considerations in Using Artificial Intelligence (AI) for Evangelism by the 21st Century Church

It has become very obvious, that AI is becoming more pervasive by the day. To this end, concerns about its ethical and social impacts keep intensifying. The major concern centres on issues such as protecting data privacy, handling bias in AI systems, and stopping AI from widening societal imbalances. Other discussions are seen in the area of ethical implications of AI in various domains like surveillance, weaponry, and law enforcement (Etienne, 2024).

Furthermore, the emergence of AI generated content like, deep fakes, raises doubts about the authenticity of digital information. It underscores the urgent need for comprehensive ethical guidelines and regulations

frameworks to ensure the responsible and fair deployment of AI technologies in evangelism and other engagements. Apart from this, integrating ethics and moral principles into AI systems poses significant challenges, raises concerns about the potential for unchecked AI advancement, leading to existential threats such as the AI singularity (Afanugo and Molokwu, 2024).

Furthermore, other ethical and moral concerns to be considered while deploying AI by the 21st century Church include: concerns about human autonomy, human dignity, worth and value, equality and freedom of human person.

On concerns about human autonomy, (Fourie, 2020) said that, “technology often creates a misleading perception of autonomy and independence. As people experience substitution and augmentation by technology, they may undervalue human interaction.” This notion also extends to religious contexts, when thinking of using AI for evangelism

Speaking on the ethics of human dignity, studies show that, there are apprehensions about the potentials for the growing use of AI to diminish human life and dignity as machines acquire the capacity to execute tasks previously deemed exclusive to humans. For example, Goertzel, Monroe, Mossbridge, Gress, Strauss, Evanow and Mayet (2017) initiated the “Loving AI” project to develop software that enables humanoid robots to interact with humans in loving and compassionate ways. Human dignity is rooted in the belief that every individual has inherent worth and value simply by being human. This means that using AI should not entail disrespecting human dignity. All people should be treated respectfully and never be reduced to mere objects or instruments (Anderson et al, 2018).

Human dignity entails that everyone be treated as equals and that no one should be discriminated against based on race, gender, religion, sexual orientation, or other characteristics. Ntoutsu (2020), discussed ethical concerns about bias and discrimination in AI-based decision-making systems. Human dignity includes freedom from slavery, torture, and other abuse forms and the right to freedom of speech, thought, and religion. The growing concern is that autonomous weapons, cybercrime and weaponised, ill-intended information will lead to mayhem. All these must be noted by the Church while engaging AI for evangelism. Discussing further on the ethical and moral implications of AI to the society, (Duggai, 2024), outlined some challenges noted. Such challenges include: limited adaptability, costly development, job displacement, loss of emotional intelligence, lack of innovation, laziness and dependence. All these have a way in which they affect not just the Church but the entire society.

Dangers of Ignoring Ethical Considerations in Artificial Intelligence (AI) Usage: A Theological Concern

Using AI in evangelism has great advantages. However, Afolaranmi (2019), affirmed that, “as good as these modern technologies like AI, are in building the educational ministries of a local Church, there are some misuses and abuses of these technological tools that are negatively affecting the Church.” Contemporary issues raised about AI, have sparked discussions in the field of Church and theology (Ham, 2020). Conversations about post-modernity, globalisation, and post-colonialism have dominated the corridor of discussions in recent times. Van (2020), noted “that the significant influence of technologies has been overlooked due to a lack of awareness and comprehension of their potential impacts.” Emerging technologies like AI, has greater potentials to transform society in significant ways, yet numerous individuals remain uninformed about the potential risks and advantages linked to these technologies.

Allen and ChatGPT (2023), accentuated that, “one significant concern regarding AI in Christian religious settings revolves around playing god.” Critics have argued that the emergence of advanced technologies like AI systems with human-like intelligence can be seen as an attempt by man to assume God-like powers, potentially challenging divine authority and agency. This concept of playing god raises questions about the boundaries of human agency and the limits of human creativity in relation to God’s sovereignty.

The use of AI in decision-making processes within sacred settings raises theological concerns regarding human agency and the authority of God. If AI systems make autonomous decisions, there is a potential for these decisions to contradict religious/theological (or even commonly held moral) principles. Since the fall, theological tension has prompted Christians to reflect on the balance between human responsibility and the guidance of a higher power (Allen and ChatGPT, 2023).

Furthermore, Smuha (2021), affirmed that, "AI systems possess the potential to inflict individual, collective and societal harm, violate privacy, and transgress human rights, leading to physical, emotional, or psychological damage to individuals and society." Individual harm occurs when wrongful impediments obstruct one or more interests of an individual. AI systems risk perpetuating or even intensifying bias and discrimination, potentially resulting in the unjust treatment of individuals or groups based on race, gender, or socioeconomic status (Benjamin, 2019).

Using Artificial Intelligence (AI) in Ministry the Right Way

This research identified the essence of AI in expanding the frontiers evangelism by the contemporary Church. However, it is very important to note that there are better ways to using it to avoid the dangers that may come as a result of its misuse, as already noted.

In the light of the above, Musonda (2023), outlined six healthy ways through which the Church can use AI for evangelism today. These include: "using chat GPT to repurpose sermons; using AI to generate images to capture audience during sermons; using AI to create captivating social media posts; using AI to write newsletters for Church members; using AI in writing blog articles for Church website; along with using AI to create contents in multiple languages thereby cutting across races and reaching a wider audience." To ensure that AI is used ethically and morally, it is important to respect the privacy and autonomy of those being evangelized and to avoid any strategies that could be perceived as invasive or manipulative, especially, in countries with multifaceted tribes, languages, and cultures; not ignoring the diverse religions of the people. It is a fact that once AI is programmed, trained, designed and tested adequately, it can never be biased or flawed. To this end, there is need to ensure that the data and algorithms used are accurate and unbiased. This equally facilitates the smooth, trustworthy and reliable operation of AI. There is no inherent reason for the Church not to utilize AI. AI can be a highly effective medium of reaching people with the gospel message especially in the contemporary digital age. It is obvious that any Christian Church that has used YouTube, Google, Facebook, and other social media platforms had actually used AI. AI should simply be used in ways that align to biblical values and principles. Adequate caution should be taken to avoid using it in ways that could harm others or violate their privacy (Musonda, 2023).

Furthermore, AI can assist in evangelism via the reposition of sermons. In the contemporary fast-paced world, not everyone engages with the Church's YouTube sermons. Mankind's attention spans have shortened, making it challenging for people to invest time in lengthy content. They reflect that leveraging AI allows the Church to effectively compact and remodel sermons for various platforms and groups. The Church can convert them into text for blogs or create bite-sized social media posts, thereby opening up numerous possibilities. This is quite relevant in the contemporary situation where everyone is agog with social media content creation and news blogging (Godkulture Team, 2023).

The 21st century Church can employ advanced AI tools to improve the sanctification process for believers. This is possible in the following areas: translating the Bible, distributing and fostering its reading around the world; and the spreading of spiritual revival through mediated algorithms. There are clear future positive prospects pertinent to the integration of AI in the Church missionary enterprise (La Cruz and Mora, 2024).

Conclusion

The contemporary world and its systems are in constant flux. New ideas and modes of approach to complex challenges are emerging daily. Any institution, facility or individual that abhors AI will definitely have themselves to blame. The Church is not left out, especially, in the area of involving sophisticated technologies in mission and evangelism. The use of Artificial intelligence and its specifics has assisted the Church greatly in advancing the mission activities in the 21st century. The Church should know that the brain behind AI is human intelligence. The creator of mankind is God. Human intelligence is equally reinforced and evoked by God Himself. There is nothing wrong in engaging the services of AI in evangelism by the Church. It will only facilitate evangelical expertise and make for wider coverage. Care however, should be taken in the ethical and moral implications of using AI in advancing God's kingdom, as AI is not free from human errors and shortcomings. In using AI, the Church should ensure that the gospel message is not bereft of human and spiritual touch in the process of incorporating AI in evangelism. The Church should not leave the work of evangelism to be championed by AI. Man-kind should always be at the helm of affairs; maintaining steady connection to God as well as exerting empathy towards the target mission audience.

Recommendations

The work further recommends that:

1. The Church, while integrating AI in missionary work should be ready to be accountable for its shortcomings. This should make the Church not to take ethical issues involved in using AI for granted.
2. Ethical considerations surrounding AI and society's trust in it deserve further consideration. There is need for transparency, accountability, and proper regulation in AI development to foster trust and ensure responsible social integration, if the Church or any organization, will involve it in their activities.
3. Finally, organizing workshops and seminars to create awareness and educate Church leaders about the potential of AI in enhancing Church missions along with reaching wider audience should be organized by those at the helm of authorities.

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